

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS BETWEEN ISLAMIC AND CONVENTIONAL BANKS CHARACTERISTICS' IMPACT ON THEIR RISK-TAKING BEHAVIOUR

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Abstract

This study provides a comparative analysis of the risk-taking behavior of Islamic and conventional banks, emphasizing the distinctive characteristics that influence their approaches to risk management. Islamic banks, guided by Maqasid al-Shariah, adhere to unique ethical principles that shape their governance structures, financial instruments, and risk profiles. The research examines the differences in common and specific risks faced by both banking systems and analyzes internal and external factors influencing their risk-taking behavior. The role of the Shariah Supervisory Board (SSB) in shaping risk decisions within Islamic banks is critically evaluated. The study also highlights the discrepancies between theoretically recognized risks and practical risk management within Islamic banks, offering insights into the implications for banking stability and performance.

Keywords: Islamic banks, conventional banks, risk-taking behavior, Maqasid al-Shariah, Shariah Supervisory Board, risk assessment, financial stability, profit-loss sharing.

Introduction

Banks, regardless Islamic or conventional, serve a single function of mediating between economic agents with deficit and surplus finances. Islamic banks must, simultaneously, observe higher ethical objectives - *Maqasid al-Shariah*. Such observance of Shariah rules¹ leads to emergence of unique corporate, operational, instrumental features that are only specific to Islamic Banks (IB). Firstly, Islamic bank's corporate structure comprises both *Board of Directors* (BOD) and *Shariah Supervisory Board* (SSB), unlike their conventional counterparts only having the former. Secondly, IBs adopt *risk-sharing* (profit-sharing) model in contrast to interest-based one in traditional banks (Ehsan Ullah & Sabirzyanov, 2015). Risk-free business practices and excessive risk-taking are absolutely prohibited in Islamic Finance. Thus, the concept of *essential risk-taking* emerges which is inherent in all business transactions.

These peculiarities, according to Hassan & Mollah (2018), correspondingly, transform **risk-taking behaviour** of IBs and result in more complex risk types. The following essay attempts to critically analyse how IB characteristics influence risk-taking decisions in comparison with traditional banking, firstly, by analysing

their risk profiles, followed by various factors shaping such behaviour.

Discussion

To comprehend and compare risk-taking behaviour of Islamic and conventional banks, its crucial to identify how risk map of both are deviated from each other (figure 1). Many studies highlight that IBs' exposure to risks can be classified into two categories: (1) *common risks* and (2) *specific risks* (Ahmed & Khan, 2007; Zainol & Kassim, 2012; Salem, 2013). Risks found in both Islamic and conventional banks are regarded as *common*, such as operational, liquidity, credit, and market risks. For instance, Sorwar *et al.* (2016) emphasizes the characteristic similarity of market risk in both banking industries. Whereas, Akkizidiz & Khandelwal (2007) suggest that even such generic risks may differ in implications and severity in IBs. Furthermore, the exposure frequency to identical risks might also greatly vary in them (Ariffin *et al.*, 2009).

Specific risks of IBs

Due to principal differences in the business model, corporate governance and contractual basis, there are several unique risks in Islamic banking (Hassan *et al.*, 2019).

Figure 1. Common versus specific risks faced by IBs.2

¹ To ensure Shariah compliance, Islamic banks have to avoid certain prohibitions: (1) charging interest; (2) excessive uncertainty; (3) gambling; (4) investing in unethical businesses (e.g. alcohol, pork, pornography).

² Developed by author via 'Mural' software

As depicted in figure 1, the first inherent risk in the nature of IBs is *Shariah non-compliance risk*. It is considered to arise when there is a deviation from the theory of Shariah law in practice (Alhammadi *et al.*, 2020). At the same time, it is classified to be within the category of operational risks by Rhanoui & Belkhoutout (2019). Shariah non-compliance risk mainly results from the negligence of Shariah Supervisory Board (SSB), and according to Salem (2013), it is exacerbated by the challenge of maintaining Shariah compliance while operating in globalised financial system preoccupied by conventional model. *Rate of return risk* is the second risk (figure 2), and emanates from the 'expected profit' instead of 'guaranteed interest' in IBs (Chattha *et al.*, 2020). Accordingly, byproduct of lower rate of return is *displaced commercial risk*. Rouetbi *et al.* (2023) argues that lower rate of return encourages profit-driven investors to withdraw their deposits and thus, IBs will be under pressure to 'compensate for the loss' waiving certain percentage from bank's profit. According to Abedifar *et al.*, (2013) however, this

'trade-off' practice is a partial deviation from authentic profit-loss sharing principles of Islamic Finance. Lastly, *equity investment risk* is the third most mentioned inherent risk and directly reflects the nature of murabah/musharakah contracts – equity participation (Helmy, 2012).

Interestingly, Rhanoui & Belkhoutout (2019) suggest that these theoretically recognized risks are not all identified, assessed and managed in practice. For example, based on their study³ conducted on IBs in Malaysia, *displaced commercial risk* and *equity investment risk* are hardly ever reported in their risk profile.

Factors effecting bank risk-taking behaviour

Magnis *et al.* (2023) attest that risk-taking decisions of banks are affected by a number of complex factors, typically classified as internal and external (figure 2). *External factors* typically comprise, but not limited to, economic condition of the region, inflation rate, monetary policy, market concentration, political issues, etc.

Figure 2. External factors effecting bank risk-taking behaviour.⁴

To illustrate the impact of *external regulators*, high capital ratio requirements imposed by Basel II had positive effect on credit risk of banks in MENA (Middle east and North Africa) region, moderating their risk-taking (Maghyereh & Awartani, 2014). Regarding the impact of *competitiveness*, many studies postulate the positive relationship between market competition and risk-taking of banks (Mateev *et al.*, 2022). According

to Allen & Gale (2004), such high risk-taking behaviour of banks in competitive markets is to maintain their profitability. As illustrated in the figure 2, these factors impact banks risk-taking decisions externally.

Internal factors

At the same time, there are certain characteristics, e.g. ownership structure, size, capitalization, location, etc. that differ from bank to bank, and are only peculiar to the bank individually (figure 3).

³ See appendix 1

⁴ Developed by author via 'Mural' software

Figure 3. Internal factors (bank characteristics) effecting risk-taking behaviour.⁵

These characteristics tailor the risk-appetite within an each bank in a unique way, thus are called *internal factors*. Likewise risk types, internal factors can be classified as *common* and *IB specific* characteristics. Below are given 3 major common internal factors and how they impact risk-taking behaviour of both banking systems.

Common characteristics

Ownership structure can influence banks in two dimensions: (1) *ownership concentration*⁶ and (2) *nature of owner profiles* (Mateev *et al.*, 2022). Although, theoretically, the higher concentrated ownership is expected to accelerate more pronounced risk-taking, from empirical perspective the scenario is quite ambiguous. While Leaven & Levine (2009) proved the relationship between concentrated ownership and greater risk, the reverse is demonstrated by Shehzad *et al.* (2010) in relation to credit risk. The latter finding is further supported by the search of Srairi (2013): the negative association, i.e. banks with high ownership concentration experienced much lower insolvency and asset risks. This can be explained by the argument of Burkart *et al.* (1997), once large shareholders put high pressure on monitoring, it discourages bank managers to initiate new risky investment opportunities.

Nature of owners, namely family-owned, company/private-owned and state-owned, also plays vital role. Anderson *et al.* (2003) found that family banks tend to engage in less risky activities to ensure bank's survival in long term. Moreover, Srairi (2013) compliments that as bank managers and owners form singly entity - the family itself, there is no misalignment in risk preferences. This, in turn minimises agent-principal problem, where the interests of principal (shareholder) and agent (manager) mismatch in non-family banks.. Private commercial banks, reasonably, are found to be more risk averse by Zheng *et al.* (2017), whereas state-owned banks suffer from higher insolvency risk compared to private banks. Positive relationship between government ownership and risk can be explained by the argument of Iannotta *et al.* (2007), which signifies that risk-taking decisions are dictated by bureaucrats biased with political interests.

• **Bank size** is typically considered to be strong determinant of risk-taking (Fernandes *et al.*, 2021). Significant negative correlation between size and riskiness of banks is empirically identified by many studies, as demonstrated larger banks have wider range of opportunities to better diversify their portfolios (Saif-Alyousfi & Saha, 2021; AlAbbad *et al.*, 2019; Srairi, 2013). Nevertheless, large banks practically can take bigger risks as they are capable of easily managing in case of misfortune occurrence (Fernandes *et al.*, 2021).

• **Capitalisation** factor is rather similar to bank size: banks with low capitalisation increase the risk, while better capitalised banks are characterised with decreased risk-taking (Anh, 2022; Alman, 2012). Although capitalisation's role in risk-taking decisions does not necessarily result in disputes among scholars, an exception is observed by Saif-Alyousfi & Saha (2021) during Global financial crisis. Study findings illustrate that unlike pre- and post-crisis period, highly capitalized banks took more risky activities during financial crisis compared to ones with low capitalisation.

All above mentioned *internal factors* are common in both Islamic and conventional banking (figure 3). These *bank characteristics* (ownership structure, size, capitalization level) shape risk-taking decisions of both banking systems in identical manner, i.e. large bank size and capitalization result in less risk in both banks in identical manner (Saif-Alyousfi & Saha, 2021).

IB specific characteristics

Shariah feature of IBs reflects in their corporate governance structure. Unlike 'single-layer' structure comprising of Board of Directors (BOD) in conventional banks, IB employ 'multi-layer' governance with Shariah Supervisory Board (SSB) in addition to BOD (Mollah & Zaman, 2015). SSB actively participates in supervising the operations, product development and managerial decisions to ensure compliance of IBs. Such a close engagement indispensably intensifies SSB's impact on risk-taking behaviour.

The role of SSB in risk-taking

On the one hand, Mollah *et al.* (2016) claims that governance structure in IBs encourages high risk-taking, in turn leading to better performance. From conventional perspective, accordingly, Fortin *et al.* (2010)

⁵ Developed by author via 'Mural' software

⁶ According to Alhababsah (2019), it is defined as 'the proportion of shares held by a single individual or entity'.

argues that more risk is taken if there is strong governance mechanism. This argument that high risk-taking manner of IBs may lead to enhanced financial performance is empirically supported by search finding of Sueb *et al.* (2022) conducted on 70 IBs in 18 countries. In stark contrast, on the other hand, it is argued by Prasjo *et al.* (2022) that risk-taking imposes considerable adverse effects on IBs' performance, even further reinforcing their position by statement that low risk-taking is an indicator of high efficiency. Though some scholars, such as Nomran *et al.* (2018) prefer more neutral approach toward SSB's role, asserting that SSB moderates risk-taking behaviour of managers, to balance the interests of depositors and shareholders. Despite ongoing disputes about whether SSB encourages or discourages risky decisions among academics, its strong association with risk-taking of IBs clearly can be denied.

Impact of different SSB attributes in risk-taking

Likewise, the exact manner of how various SSB features, such as size, education level, diversity, etc impact risk-taking has been debated continually.

- According to Alman (2012) large **SSB size** encourages loan portfolio risk-taking. Consistently, Alabbad *et al.* (2019) and Safiullah & Shamsuddin (2017) endorse this view by highlighting positive correlation between increase in SSB size and active risk-taking behaviour. It is also mentioned that such association is more pronounced in decentralized SSB, which are ruled by individual banks, compared to state-ruled centralized SSB. However, in case of conventional banks, smaller BOD is associated with particularly risky decisions (Pathan, 2009).

- Similarly, high **quality of SSB** (i.e. education, expertise and doctoral qualifications) is claimed by Mukhibad & Setiawan (2022) to result in increasingly risky decisions. As Grassa (2013) argues, however, increased SSB quality means better supervision, which in turn decreases risk-taking. This view is confirmed by Nguyen (2021), as he found that enhanced effectiveness of SSB might constrain risk-taking in IBs.

Conclusion

In conclusion, IBs developed peculiar business model as a financial intermediary while observing Shariah rules. This peculiarity not only reflects in their corporate governance and financial instruments, but also results in unique risk-taking behaviour. This essay offers several concluding statements after thorough critical analysis of relevant literature. Firstly, IBs avoid two extremes: zero and excessive risk-taking (Ehsan-Ullah & Sabirzyanov, 2015). In other words, IBs take essential risk which is inherent in nature of commercial activities, instead of attempting to avoid all possible risks like conventional banks do. Secondly, there is marked difference between risk profiles of both banking systems, with that of IBs being more diverse and complicated. Thirdly, although there are some common external and internal factors that similarly affect risk-taking decision of both banks, IBs have additional specific bank determinants impacting their risk-taking. Finally, an extra layer in governance structure of IBs - Shariah Supervisory Board (SSB) - which monitors and directly influences risk-taking behaviour of IBs. The fact that religious belief certainly effects managerial decisions i.e. risk-taking is even proved from Christian perspective by Abakah & Li (2023).

Limitations & Recommendations

This essay, however, has limitations in terms of covering all bank characteristics that impact risk-taking decisions, e.g. financial interconnectedness, fintech usage, foreign ownership, language etc. and IB specific risks, e.g. fiduciary risk, mark-up risk, legal risk, commodity risk, etc.

Regarding recommendations, some implications of language usage in bank risk-taking should be studied in more depth. Interestingly, certain languages with more pronounced usage of future tense, is associated with more risk-taking and bank crisis (Osei-Tutu & Weill, 2020). Nevertheless, the impact of CEO/SSB changes, who speak languages with heavy stress on future tense, to the ones with relatively low usage and vice versa are understudied research area.

Appendix

Table 1. Risk reports of IBs in Malaysia.⁷

	Bank Islam Malaysia Berhad	Bank Muamalat Malaysia Berhad	Kuwait Finance House Malaysia Berhad	MBSB Bank Berhad	Agrobank
Credit risk	Reported	Reported	Reported	Reported	Reported
Market risk	Reported	Reported	Reported	Reported	Reported
Liquidity risk	Reported	Reported	Reported	Reported	Reported
Operational risk	Reported	Reported	Reported	Reported	Reported
Shari'a non-compliance risk	Reported	Reported	Reported	Reported	Reported
Rate of return risk	Reported	Unreported	Unreported	Unreported	Reported
Equity investment risk	Reported	Reported	Unreported	Unreported	Unreported
Displaced commercial risk	Unreported	Unreported	Unreported	Unreported	Unreported

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